

User Experience and International Conference Workshops content

D2.5 version 2.5

May 2018

merlin

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 780.460

Copyright © MERLIN Consortium
<https://merlin-ict.eu>

MERLIN
Methodologies for Researcher
Led INnovations
GA No. 780.460
ICT-32-2017 EU H2020

Confidentiality Level: PU

<i>Document Type</i>	Contract Deliverable	
<i>Document & WP No.</i>	D2.5	WP2
<i>Document Title</i>	User Experience and International Conference Workshops content	
<i>Release date</i>	Version 2.5 – 31/05/2018	

Executive summary

This document, D2.5 — User Experience and International Conference Workshops content – is a deliverable of the MERLIN project, which is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 under Grant Agreement #780460, and has been prepared by taking into account the template of the "Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020" and the "Fact Sheet: Open Access in Horizon 2020".

Merlin aims to foster and accelerate the transfer of knowledge from the projects funded in FP7 and H2020, be it on the form of license agreement, patent or ideally, spinoff or startup to directly exploit them, by organising practical hands-on workshops; meet ups with potential partners, customers and investors; and by attending scientific conferences to reach a wider public. The programme will equip participants with knowledge, skills and a network to generate market-led business models to unlock potential and accelerate this journey.

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide content for the "User experience" and for the activities organized in International Conferences.

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 780.460

Copyright © MERLIN Consortium
<https://merlin-ict.eu>

Document Control Page			
Title	User Experience and International Conference Workshops content		
Creator	PSTP		
Description	Description of the content used in the workshop – User Experience and International Conference content.		
Review status	Action	Person/Partner	Date
	Completed by WP Leader	Natalia Rymarczuk	20/05/2018
	Approved by Peer Panel	Pedro Sánchez	27/05/2018
	Approved by QA	Diego Alonso	31/05/2018
Distribution	Confidential		CO

Revision history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
1.0	10/05/2018	Natalia Rymarczuk	First version of the deliverable.
1.8	20/05/2018	Natalia Rymarczuk	Second version of the deliverable.
2.0	27/05/2018	Pedro Sánchez	Final version

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	5
1.1. Audience	5
1.2. Structure	6
2. Workshop "User Experience"	7
2.1. General information about the workshop	7
2.2. Preliminars	7
2.3. Slides and guide for Trainers	8
3. Workshop "International Conferences"	29
3.1. General information about the workshop	29
3.2. Preliminars	29
3.3. Slides and guide for Trainers	30
4. Conclusions	52

1. Introduction

This deliverable (D2.5) — User Experience and International Conference Workshops content – is a deliverable of the MERLIN project, which is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 under Grant Agreement #780460 and has been prepared by taking into account the template of the "Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020"¹ and the "Fact Sheet: Open Access in Horizon 2020"². The purpose of the deliverable is to provide a description of the material that will be used in two workshops. The topics of which are user experience and international conference workshops content. All members of the Consortium will use the same content for conducting the workshops at their locations.

Funding in ICT project under FP7 and H2020 totals over 11.000 million € by the end of the current work programme. Stimulated and supported by these programs, many researchers in universities, institutes and SMEs have worked hard on developing new ground-breaking technologies and disruptive services. But when it comes to commercialize the results or create a company, these researchers are unsure on how to proceed. MERLIN project, funded in the context of the EC initiative *Innovation Radar*, wants to start changing this situation by organizing a set of activities aiming:

- To stimulate a greater interest in the scientific community to view their research results as potential opportunities to be exploited with the correct business model.
- To equip researchers with modern, need-first and market-led methodologies that will help them to shape their ideas and outputs into innovations to be ready for market validation and posterior commercialization.
- To introduce the rich European entrepreneurship ecosystem and the opportunities it offers to create and support startups on their journey.

Among the planned activities, it is worth highlighting the following:

- Organisation of 45 practical workshops covering state-of-the-art innovation and entrepreneurship methodologies in 8 European cities.
- Organisation of 5 workshops in scientific conferences to reach more researchers and engage them with the activities organized by MERLIN and other ICT-32 projects.
- Organisation of 8 meet ups with potential partners, customers and investors by the end of each year.
- Organisation of 4 webinars on SME growth and new business models for public-private partnership.

The deliverable describes: methodologies and case- study examples of how it is used in real-life business situations, advice and guidelines on implementation, homework to be done for the researchers to assess and/or draft strategies for commercialisation of their inventions or applied research.

1.1. Audience

The main intended audience for this document is the MERLIN project consortium and the European Commission, but also workshop attendees and general public.

The target audience of the workshops are researchers and startups from the ICT field.

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

² https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/sites/horizon2020/files/FactSheet_Open_Access.pdf

1.2. Structure

The structure of the document is as follows:

- Section 2 presents the content of the User Experience workshop.
- Section 3 presents the content of the International Conference workshop
- Section 4 summarizes the conclusions.

2. Workshop "User Experience"

2.1. General information about the workshop

Name of the workshop: User Experience

Name of the partner which is responsible for the content delivery: PSTP

Duration of the workshop: 4 hours

Optimal number of participants: from 20 to 30

Target groups: Junior and senior researchers, PhD students on their last years and post-doc with research results

Target group needs identified: The target group lacks knowledge on how to commercialize their products / research findings, how to find out the customer's need, how to collect, organize, evaluate and use information about the client, how to evaluate current resources and what resources will they need in the future.

Key skills to be acquired: to engage users in accordance with the User Experience philosophy and user-centred design methodology.

The main goals of the workshop:

- Understand the importance of User Experience in the design of a product or process
- Identify indicators of success
- Plot the customer journey using the 'talking out loud' method
- Identify, classify and prioritise changes to be made.

Learning methods to be applied: Kolb's Learning Cycle.

The main requirements for the venue: computer, projector, projector screen, able to seat 20-30 people

Requirements for supplies needed: Pens, markers, large sheets of paper, stopwatch or a phone with stopwatch.

2.2. Preliminars

The basic rules to have into account during the workshop are:

- No question is a silly question;
- What is said in the room stays in the room;
- Support and challenge each other.

The main purpose of the introduction of the rules for the workshop is to encourage the participants to ask questions as the questions asked will stay in the room and everyone should support and challenge each other.

The general information about the workshop is provided:

- Length of the workshop (4 hours);
- Coffee break (20 minutes);
- Slides will be shared with the participants after the workshop.

Short information about the workshop – expected length is 4 hours, there will be 1 coffee break and information regarding slide availability after the workshop – each partner can choose how to disseminate the slides after the workshop.

PRINCIPLES

- There are no bad questions
- Everything we discuss stays in the room
- Commitment and team work

3

This slide is for setting the ground rules for the workshop – encouraging the participants to ask questions, the information/questions asked will stay in the room and everyone should support and challenge each other.

About MERLIN project

MERLIN project aims to stimulate the interest in the creation of startups, spin-offs and licensing agreements among ICT researchers, providing them with the business skills that would help them to commercialize their research findings and successfully introduce them to the market, and introducing them to their local and European entrepreneurial ecosystems

Organization of more than **40 practical thematic workshops** in several European cities, including Cambridge, Madrid, Poznan, Vilnius, Berlin, Warsaw, Bucharest, Tallinn

Participation in **5 international conferences**, organizing workshops and forums

Preparation of **4 webinars** on SME growth and PPP business models

Organization of **8 meetups** with potential customers, commercial partners, and investors

<https://merlin-ict.eu>
4

Short introduction to the MERLIN project, covering the main idea and concept of it.

MERLIN partners

3 Incubators

- Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena
- University of Cambridge
- Poznan Science and Technology Park

2 Consultancy Companies

- BluSpecs
- CIVITTA

5

Short introduction about MERLIN partners.

Agenda

- Intro
- Ice breaker
- Usability testing
- Exercises
- Closing

6

Quick overlook of the workshop agenda.

what do you need?

a name card

a bingo card

a pen

sense of humour

Is not afraid of public presentations	Makes decisions quickly	Born leader	Has many friends	Has organisational skills	Avoids conflicts
Willingly selects new dishes in a restaurant	Likes planning	Draws inspiration from people	Observer	Likes to work in the morning	Appreciates peace and quiet
Prefers listening to speaking	Analytical mind	Likely to take a risk	Often spots mistakes	Likes discussions	Likes clearly defined roles/tasks
Detail-oriented	Patient	Establishes relations quickly	Optimist	A powerhouse of ideas	Cooperation motivates her/him
Enthusiastic about new ideas	Motivated by work results	Acts better under the pressure of time	Extrovert	Spontaneous	Perfectionist
not afraid to ask for help	Likes to work in the evenings	Does not avoid confrontation	Not afraid of asking questions	Feels well working in chaos	Motivated by competition

The purpose of the exercise is to let the participants get to know each other and create proper work dynamics. In this slide the trainer discusses the above-listed resources one by one, focusing on a bingo card.

rules

1. find a partner
2. Ask each other questions from the board for 1 minute
3. if you find an answer, enter your partner's name in the field
4. after each subsequent minute, you have to find a new partner
5. One name in each field is enough
6. the first person who fills in all fields shouts BINGO

1. Ask the participants to stand up and go to an area where they will be able to move freely. Tell them that they will play the game standing.
2. Ask every person to find a partner for the first round. Important: if the number of participants is not even, the trainer should (optionally):
 - ask another person, who will be present in the Room only during the game (e.g. an assistant, the second trainer, etc.),
 - suggest that one of the groups is always composed of three persons.
3. Read the principles listed on the slide aloud (points two to six). Having read the instructions, make sure that all participants understand them.
4. Inform that the trainer will measure the time and, after each minute, ask the participants to find new partners.
5. The process will be repeated by the time one of the participants fills in all fields and shouts BINGO.
6. After one of the participants shouts BINGO, several random fields from their card should be read out to check whether she/he really has entered the names properly. Such a group conversation has an additional cognitive value. If we find a mistake or an empty field, we continue the game.

Note: The game stimulates energy within the group and creates a positive atmosphere. We do not let the energy subside. Ask the participants to arrange the chairs, sit down and go on to the next task.

the same hardware; different experience

 H2020 GA #780460

10

The development of technology and the variety of solutions available on the market have led to increased awareness and increased preferences of users of products and services. Their basic essence ceases to be a criterion for making decisions - it is easy to reproduce and repeatable. A good way to distinguish and build a bond can be to engage users - making the products reflect them, in accordance with the User Experience philosophy and user-centred design methodology.

1. We have reached a point where products are of equally high quality and consumers no longer buy things, items, services. They buy experiences, values. That is why the constant development of a product and user-

oriented design have become one of the main success factors in the software/applications business. Modern management methods have been transformed into circular processes, in which change is the only constant.

2. This is a moment for a short discussion on changes in design and IT business

but what is this UX design?

A Venn diagram consisting of two overlapping circles. The left circle is dashed blue and labeled "Business goals". The right circle is solid pink and labeled "Users needs". The overlapping area in the center is labeled "UX".

 H2020 GA #780460

12

Based on the previous slide, we have a solid ground for the explanation of the origin of UX, why it has been developed and how broad this concept is: research, user interface design, motion design, interaction design, graphic design, service design, etc.

how is UX doing it?

A circular diagram with "USER CENTRIC DESIGN" in the center. Five smaller circles are arranged around it, connected by a blue line. The steps are: PLAN (top-left), RESEARCH (top-right), DESIGN (right), ADAPT (bottom), and MEASURE (bottom-left).

 H2020 GA #780460

13

Describe shortly user centric design as one of the leading design trends. It can be compared to Design Thinking, Service Design and Lean Startup. Say that young businesses use agile methods based on very similar concepts not only in visual design, but also in development (that is, in every phase of product development).

Usability testing methods will be the main subject of the workshop. This issue is often neglected and taken into account too late – when something does not work, does not sell, nobody uses the product.

1. Shortly discuss the usability testing process in product development
2. Point out that testing can be conducted in every design phase
3. Ask the participants about their usability testing experience

Here we discuss individual usability testing methods divided into quantitative and qualitative studies as well as studies analysing users' behaviours and attitudes.

The left side of the graph will (probably) be discussed during the previous workshop – customer journey, customer development. It should be pointed out that there is no universal prescription for usability testing. Everything depends on the context, product and time

The above methods are the main subject of the workshop. A short discussion to check if anyone knows these methods and has conducted such studies.

Facebook has more than 1 000 versions running at the same time – the ultimate a/b tests.

A/B testing

50 % visitors see variation A → Variation A → 23% conversion

50 % visitors see variation B → Variation B → 11% conversion

merlin
H2020 GA #780460

18

This is a moment for the explanation of A/B tests, pointing out that they should not be too complicated at the beginning. Careful selection of testing elements is crucial. Good practices include testing the smallest amounts of elements. One should preferably start with one, e.g. the content of the headline, CTA button.

In this example, Variation A has a red header, and Variation B has a green one. After dividing traffic equally between the two, Variation A generated a 23% conversion rate, and Variation B generated a 11% conversion rate. That’s a significant lift, and if implemented site-wide, it could make a huge impact on this site’s conversion rates. Of course, this is a hypothetical test — but real tests can produce similar results.

A/B testing

25 % visitors see variation A → Variation A → 23% conversion

25 % visitors see variation B → Variation B → 11% conversion

25 % visitors see variation C → Variation C → 11% conversion

25 % visitors see variation D → Variation D → 11% conversion

merlin
H2020 GA #780460

19

More than two options, Multivariate Testing.

The more things we test, the more complex the entire study is (exponentially), and the results are not always clear.

Testing campaign example:

1. Describe the above graph
2. show how the complexity of research grows exponentially, adding new elements
3. point out how important it is to start with simple tests of a single element

1. Conclude that, in the above example, showing the best example is simple, but not everything is clear with elements that affect each other.

pros and cons - talking out loud

Get clear evidence

Test new ideas

Optimise one step at a time

Answer specific design questions

Can take a lot of time

Only works for specific goals

Doesn't improve a dud

Could end up with constant testing

22

Pros of A/B testing

Get clear evidence

It's easy to see how many users complete a transaction with site A over site B. The evidence is based on real behaviour, so is hard data of the type that money men love (and can be presented in a simple-looking, hard hitting chart).

Test new ideas

If you have an innovative idea for an existing site, A/B testing provides hard proof as to whether it works or not. However, you will need to implement that big idea in hard code before you can test it this way.

Optimise one step at a time

If you run a large site, or many sites, then A/B testing is a fantastic opportunity to "patch" test, by starting out in a small corner and then working up to the main pages of the site. However, can smaller site users with less traffic afford to gamble with real users by giving half of them a site experience that might not be optimal?

Answer specific design questions

Are green buttons better than red ones for your site design? This and many other questions can be answered by A/B testing as they allow the designer to test different colours, placement of buttons, page layouts, different images which are all good areas to slowly improve a website.

Cons of A/B testing

Can take lots of time and resources

A/B testing can take a lot longer to set up than other forms of testing. Setting up the A/B system can be a resource and time hog, although third-party services can help. Depending on the company size, there may be endless meetings about which variables to include in the tests. Once a set of variables have been agreed, designers and coders will need to effectively work on doubling the amount of information. In addition, in order to get conclusive results, tests can take weeks and months for low-traffic sites.

Only works for specific goals

This kind of testing is ideal if you want to solve one dilemma: which product page gives me the best results? But, if your goals are less easy to measure, pure A/B testing won't provide those answers.

Doesn't improve a dud

If your site had usability problems to begin with and the variations are just an iteration of that, it is likely to still have the fundamental flaws that your other site contained. A/B Testing won't reveal these types of flaws or reveal user frustration and you won't be able to pick up on the reasons behind the site's problems. Just because A resulted in more sales, it is only in relation to B. Removing the original usability issue could be much quicker to identify and produce much better results.

Could end up with constant testing

Once the test is over, that is it. The data is useless for anything else. Further A/B tests will have to start from a new baseline and other types of testing will only likely be applied to the more successful site, when they could have found equally useful information from the rejected version.

6 steps to good testing

- 1. Determine your goal**
- 2. Decide which page to test**
- 3. Select elements to A/B test**
- 4. Design your test**
- 5. Let your test accumulate data**
- 6. Document or implement your results**

Coffee break – 20 min.

Fika – nice Swedish tradition – A social cup of coffee. Main rules indicated in the slide could be mentioned.

The Golden Rules of Fika (general information – not for the presentation):

1. Being asked to Fika, or asking someone to Fika is perfectly acceptable office behaviour.
2. Fika can be at a pre-arranged time, or be called unannounced. It should occur at least once per day.
3. There must always be at least one type of hot drink and one type of sweet pastry involved in every Fika session. A selection of both is even better.
4. Anyone can join your Fika unannounced as long as they stick to the rules of play.
5. A good Fika should last at least 10 minutes. Not including warming up the scenario (the kettle, don't get smutty).
6. There is no time limit to a good Fika session. You will know when it's over. It gets awkward.
7. Usage of laptops or mobile phones is not allowed whilst you are Fika-ing. Anyone found sneaking a peek should be reprimanded immediately, or asked to leave the Fika session.

mouse and eye tracking

f-shape lives

Introduction to tracking, it is good to mention the possibility of tracking on mobile devices.

types of maps

heatmap

Use colour-coding to indicate different levels of activities. The brighter or hotter an area is, the more interaction it represents.

Users browsing your website perform numerous activities. The functionality of a heat map involves the collection of data from clicks and the generation of a colour map based on it. A user-friendly, intuitive interface makes it possible to analyse places with the greatest number of clicks. The more intense a colour, the “hotter” a location is. Thus you find out where you should place items that are the most important to you. A heat map has filters that you can manage during the analysis. You can choose from, among other things, the date of an Internet user's entry on the website, type of browser or the resolution of the browser.

types of maps

clickmap

Clickmaps display the exact number of clicks on specific elements or links on a page – links, images, text and other elements.

27

Users often click on your website elements subconsciously, expecting that they will be transferred to the next page. They are disappointed when nothing happens. Sometimes, before they go to a particular page, they must put great effort to hit the button that transfers them to it. A click map, which shows the exact elements clicked by your users, helps you avoid such irritating situations. The information is included in a report in the form of points. As individual “clicks” are recorded, you receive information on the browser and resolution in which the site was viewed.

types of maps

envelope

The view “red”, “green”, “orange” and “blue” coloured circles which denote the total number of clicks for that specific element.

28

An activity map provides information on the effectiveness of action buttons (so-called call to action), hyperlinks and form fields. CTA buttons can be used e.g. to publish comments or confirm the purchase. An activity map determines whether they are structured properly and which ones are more popular. Data presented as numbers.

types of maps

scrollmap

A scrollmap is a visual representation of the web page scrolling behaviour of your visitors.

29

As different devices offer different types of resolution, users do not always see the same contents after entering a website. A limited area on which a website is displayed causes that some important information can be missed. It can be prevented by means of a scroll map. It shows whether the contents located outside the basic view range are viewed. Thus you know to which point your viewers “scroll” and which elements they do not see at all. Using a colour map you will easily identify elements that you should transfer to subpages and ones that you should move upwards, e.g. to the top.

eye tracking only

Fixation sequences

Based on fixation position (where?) and timing information (when?), you can generate a fixation sequence.

30

Eyetracking is nothing else than tracking eyeballs movements. The study involves tracking the first perception of certain elements with the use of a special camera recording even the tiniest movements of an eyeball. It takes place in the processes of consciousness, both the explicit and implicit one. The purpose of the study is to verify how people perceive an object that is in front of them, e.g. a website, a packaging or an advertisement. Thus we find out what a potential customer is looking at, which elements she/he focuses on and which elements she/he ignores completely. The aim is to check whether a viewer looking at a given graphic design sees the elements that we want to focus on. A simple example can be a website of a cosmetics company and checking whether the customer focuses more on the products or a model presented on a banner.

Fixation map (a map of elements that are the most eye-catching) including the trajectory of movement in other areas.

eye tracking only

Areas of Interest (AOI)

A tool to select subregions of the displayed stimuli, and to extract metrics specifically for these regions.

31

A map of proportions of looking at designated points of interest, e.g. promotions, a price list or a previously defined menu.

Let's talk - Ray Burke, case study

32

A discussion aimed to show that the studies can also be related to “physical” services, not only digital solutions. Eyetracking has a wide application in the area of advertising, sales increase and customer satisfaction. It is both a quantitative and qualitative study. Due to the fact that we obtain a physiological, measurement study result, we acquire hard, practically unquestionable data. It is a usability test, which enables us to reach the user with a particular information, thus eliminating or changing elements that they ignore completely. It leads to the increase of the effectiveness of marketing communication and the level of customer satisfaction. However, the advantages of the study are much greater. We obtain better availability of our offer, easier use of the application and lower ratio of “escapes” from the website. And, most importantly, we save time of not only our customers, but also our company's employees.

diary panel

We divide into groups.

diary panel – a sample diary

DAY 1		
DOCUMENTARY		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using a camera, record a short (5-10 minutes) film showing how you use Smart TV Show us elements that are the most important at this moment the screen, remote control and yourself. Comment what you are doing on an ongoing basis. Remember what is important to us: how you use the Smart TV function, how you turn on and use the applications, what you like and what irritates you? 		
SUPPLEMENTARY QUESTIONNAIRE		
1. Which Smart TV functions have you use today (even if you have not recorded it)?		
<input type="checkbox"/> Film	<input type="checkbox"/> Music	<input type="checkbox"/> Social services
<input type="checkbox"/> TV Schedule	<input type="checkbox"/> Games	<input type="checkbox"/> Radio
<input type="checkbox"/> Sports	<input type="checkbox"/> News	<input type="checkbox"/> Series

Other services or applications (which ones?):		
2. Which Smart TV navigation methods have you used today?		
<input type="checkbox"/> Remote control	<input type="checkbox"/> Voice	<input type="checkbox"/> Gesture
<input type="checkbox"/> Mouse	<input type="checkbox"/> Keyboard	<input type="checkbox"/> Smartphone/Tablet
3. Was there anything that you have particularly liked in your today's contact with Smart TV?		
4. Was there anything that was particularly irritating to you in your today's contact with Smart TV?		
5. Was G accompanied by anyone while using SmartTV? If so, write how many people:		

source: [Studies as a basis for user experience design](#)
Author: Iga Mościchowska, Barbara Rogoź-Turek

- Describe the diary study – It is a method in which a respondent keeps a diary, in which she/he regularly notes down activities that are the subject of the survey. For example, if we are interested in the way audiobooks are consumed, a respondent describes in the diary all moments when she/he is listening to an audiobook – what she/he is listening to, how long, on what device, where etc. <http://www.eriontheinterweb.com/2011/07/the-dos-and-donts-of-diary-studies/>
- Describe the above example of a diary – the components, forms of questions (open/closed etc.).

diary panel

working in teams,

we create a questionnaire to a study concerning any application

do not forget about the purpose of the survey

35

1. Each team should receive flipcharts, post-its, A4 sheets of paper and colourful markers.
2. We ask the teams which applications they will test; it is good to encourage the participants to test their own products.
3. once each team has selected an application, they have to decide which functionality they want to test, e.g. buying a train ticket at the website of the Polish National Railways or creating an account in an application.
4. Once the teams have selected the application, we ask them to write a scenario.
5. We ask the teams to design a diary for their study.

diary panel

carry out a study for at least 2 users

groups share users with each other

36

1. Each group chooses a researcher, who will be responsible for conducting the study, observers, who will watch carefully and note down the user's behaviours and users, who will participate in studies conducted by other teams.
2. We give the teams time to carry out the studies.
3. we finish the exercise part.

diary panel

what was the most difficult?

what was the coolest?

what are the pros and cons of this testing method?

37

1. We collect feedback from the teams, write it down on post-its and create a feedback wall.
2. don't forget to mention that a diary test is an ethnographic method – The observation of users in their “natural environment” is an invaluable source of knowledge for an experienced researcher studying user experience or, more broadly – customer experience. To this end, we can use the methodology of typical ethnographic research or modify them, adding, for example, sentences or interviews. [Making the Most of Ethnographic Research UX Magazine](#). A concise, but very good article about 5 important aspects of ethnographic research used to discover users' needs.

DON'T:

- Expect to yield insights from the diaries alone.

DO:

- Prepare your interview questions from the diaries as you receive them
- Pick up the last diary at the interview
- Arrange the final time for the interview upfront
- Ensure the interview is conducted in the most appropriate environment, you still want to see the participant “in situ”

thank You

38

Sum up the entire workshop.

3. Workshop "International Conferences"

3.1. General information about the workshop

Name of the workshop: International Conferences

Name of the partner which is responsible for the content delivery: PSTP

Duration of the workshop: 4 hours

Optimal number of participants: from 20 to 30

Target groups: Junior and senior researchers, PhD students on their last years and post-doc with research results

Target group needs identified: The target group lacks knowledge on how to commercialize their products / research findings, how to find out the customer's need, how to collect, organize, evaluate and use information about the client, how to evaluate current resources and what resources will they need in the future.

Key skills to be acquired: Know a series of commonly used entrepreneurship-related techniques, like Design Thinking, Customers Development, Customer Discovery classes, and Entrepreneurial Mind-set classes.

Learning methods to be applied: Kolb's Learning Cycle.

The main requirements for the venue: computer, projector, projector screen, able to seat 20-30 people

Requirements for supplies needed: Pens, markers, large sheets of paper, stopwatch or a phone with stopwatch.

3.2. Preliminars

The basic rules to have into account during the workshop are:

- No question is a silly question;
- What is said in the room stays in the room;
- Support and challenge each other.

The main purpose of the introduction of the rules for the workshop is to encourage the participants to ask questions as the questions asked will stay in the room and everyone should support and challenge each other.

The general information about the workshop is provided:

- Length of the workshop (4 hours);
- Coffee break (20 minutes);
- Slides will be shared with the participants after the workshop.

The MERLIN project is presented briefly, introducing the goals of the project, events (other Workshops, webinars, international conferences to be planned. Furthermore, the main information about the Consortium partners is provided.

3.3. Slides and guide for Trainers

The following images are the slides considered for training the researchers.

About MERLIN project

MERLIN project aims to stimulate the interest in the **creation of startups, spin-offs and licensing agreements** among ICT researchers, providing them with the **business skills** that would help them to commercialize their research findings and successfully introduce them to the market, and introducing them to their **local and European entrepreneurial ecosystems**

-

Organization of more than **40 practical thematic workshops** in several European cities, including Cambridge, Madrid, Poznan, Vilnius, Berlin, Warsaw, Bucharest, Tallinn
-

Participation in **5 international conferences**, organizing workshops and forums
-

Preparation of **4 webinars** on SME growth and PPP business models
-

Organization of **8 meetups** with potential customers, commercial partners, and investors

<https://merlin-ict.eu>

MERLIN project aims to equip researchers in ICT sector with business skills that would help them commercialize their research findings and successfully introduce them to the market.

MERLIN partners

3 Incubators

- Universidad Politécnic de Cartagena
- University of Cambridge
- Poznan Science and Technology Park

2 Consultancy Companies

- BluSpecs
- CIVITTA

3

3 incubators associated to ...

designing innovations

agenda

bingo!
creativity and innovation
generating new solutions
HOW to talk about innovation

The trainer reads the points, but does not discuss them in detail in order not to reveal what is going to happen in a moment.

principles

respect
openness
involvement
honesty
there are no stupid questions
constructive criticism (with respect to ideas, not people)
we address each other by our names
...

We introduce principles as suggestions. The trainer explains how he/she understands each concept. He/she asks the group whether everyone accepts the rules. He/she checks if everyone responded/nodded. He/she asks the group whether they would like to add anything. Each subsequent point that the group adds and agrees with should be placed at a slide.

If the issue is not discussed, the trainer asks the question: what are we going to do with the phones. The group is supposed to agree on the best solution they will be willing to obey. Yet, the rule: “we are here and now” should be reminded.

what do you need?

a name card

a bingo card

a pen

sense of humour

Is not afraid of public presentations	Makes decisions quickly	Team leader	Has many friends	Has organisational skills	Avoids conflicts
Willingly selects new dishes in a restaurant	Likes planning	Draws inspiration from people	Observer	Likes to work in the morning	Appreciates peace and quiet
Prefers listening to speaking	Analytical mind	Likely to take a risk	Often spots mistakes	Likes discussions	Likes clearly defined roles/tasks
Detailled	Patient	Establishes relations quickly	Optimist	A powerhouse of ideas	Cooperation motivates her/him
Enthusiastic about new ideas	Motivated by work results	Acts better under the pressure of time	Extrovert	Spontaneous	Perfectionist
not afraid to ask for help	Likes to work in the evenings	Does not avoid confrontation	Not afraid of asking questions	Feels well working in chaos	Motivated by competition

The purpose of the exercise is to let the participants get to know each other and create proper work dynamics. In this slide the trainer discusses the above-listed resources one by one, focusing on a bingo card.

principles

1. find a partner
2. ask each other questions from the board for 1 minute
3. if you get the answer, enter your partner's name in the field
4. after each subsequent minute you have to find a new partner
5. one name in each field is enough
6. the first person who fills in all fields shouts BINGO

1. Ask the participants to stand up and go to an area where they will be able to move freely. Tell them that they will play the game standing.
2. Ask every person to find a partner for the first round. Important: if the number of participants is not even, the trainer should (optionally):
 - ask another person, who will be present in the Room only during the game (e.g. an assistant, the second trainer, etc.),
 - suggest that one of the groups is always composed of three persons.
3. Read the principles listed on the slide aloud (points two to six). Having read the instructions, make sure that all participants understand them.
4. Inform that the trainer will measure the time and, after each minute, ask the participants to find new partners.
5. The process will be repeated by the time one of the participants fills in all fields and shouts BINGO.
6. After one of the participants shouts BINGO, several random fields from their card should be read out to check whether she/he really has entered the names properly. Such a group conversation has an additional cognitive value. If we find a mistake or an empty field, we continue the game.

Note: The game stimulates energy within the group and creates a positive atmosphere. We do not let the energy subside. Ask the participants to arrange the chairs, sit down and go on to the next task.

cow as the lead

create groups

draw as many ideas with the cow as a lead

1 idea = 1 drawing

post-it, marker, 5 min

we present

Using the energy that was created during the previous exercise, we approach the first task creatively.

1. The aim: in this exercise, the participants should let their imagination run free. The trainer encourages to generate even the fanciest ideas: stupid, smart, unrealistic ones, there should be plenty of them, the participants should not judge each other, but focus on the quantity. We do not introduce strict rules to ensure the contrast between less and more structured exercises.
2. The trainer should help the participants to form groups, preferably 4-6 persons. You should not let the participants form teams themselves, as it may cause discomfort among some of them, especially if they do not know each other.

<http://dannybeckettjr.com/2011/12/business-exercise-the-silly-cow/>

Note:

Ask them to first define some characteristics of a cow (produces milk, eats all day, makes a mooing sound, etc.). Tell them to use those characteristics to come up with an innovative business model based on a cow. Give them 5 minutes.

Keep in mind that this exercise can backfire, as it is indeed quite silly. But it has been tested with senior executives, accountants, risk managers, and entrepreneurs, and is usually a great success. The goal is to take people out of their day-to-day business routines and show them how readily they can generate ideas by disconnecting from orthodoxies and letting their creative juices flow.

ready, steady, cow ...

..... 5 min

It is important to sum up the exercise. Talk to the groups, ask questions:

- How many ideas did they have.
- Was there enough time.
- Which solutions do they like the most?.

let's talk ...

It is a moment for a dialogue, summarising the exercise and talking about the experience. In order to make people express their opinions, you should ask open questions, motivating for answers longer than yes or no. We suggest questions such as:

- What made your work easier during the Silly Cow?
- What made the work more difficult?

Your aim is to let the participants share their observations and feelings with others. The trainer writes down all the answers in the form of two lists on a flipchart/board: factors stimulating and hindering creativity.

Once the trainer has finished to write the answers down, he/she summarises both lists. The concept we are striving for is the fact that certain factors around us can have a positive and negative influence on creative processes and that creativity, just like muscles, can be properly trained by means of appropriate tools and space. Design Thinking is one of these tools.

generating new solutions and stimulating creativity

13

Silly Cow followed by discussion is an introduction to next part of the workshop. Participants will learn about two approaches which are:

- Design Thinking – focused on customers/users needs,
- SCAMPER – focused on search for innovation in existing product

It is important to outline that there are many tools which can guide through innovation generation process. We discuss two and create new ideas using one of them- SCAMPER.

Design Thinking

David Kelley is the founder of the design firm IDEO and a professor at Stanford University. He has received several honours for his contribution to design and design education. Watch a film about creative confidence <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=16p9YRF0l-g>.

A note for the trainer: if a longer workshop is held during the conference, we recommend developing this part by presenting the film to the participants. If the workshop is 4 hours long, you should only refer to David Kelley's words. And point out that IDEO uses the Design Thinking methodology.

Slide 15: Add D. Kelley's film to extend the workshop <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=16p9YRF0I-g>

We shortly discuss the tool used by IDEO to solve problems, which makes novices feel the so-called Creative Confidence. More information: <https://www.ideo.com/blogs/inspiration/what-is-design-thinking> “Design thinking is a process for creative problem solving.” – Coe Leta Stafford, Managing Director IDEO U.

When we think about design thinking, the first word that comes to **mind is human**. For example, what's the human need behind that business need?

Design thinking encourages organizations to focus on the people they're creating for and leads to human-centred products, services, and internal processes. The core of design thinking is getting actionable and knowing your questions. It's about simple mind-set shifts or ways of asking questions differently—a new way to look at problems.

Why Is Design Thinking Important?

It reduces the risk associated with launching new ideas.

It helps organizations learn faster.

It generates solutions that are innovative, not just incremental.

3 Essential Aspects of Design Thinking

Empathy (human-centred)

Ideation (generating a lot of ideas)

Experimentation

Slide 17:

MRI https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=f1H_L9ezZHk

Before showing the video please give short comment: „We will watch short short story of an engineer who took part in designing new MRI”

After the presentation we comment on the film. We point out that the focus was on users' needs, in this case both parents and children. In order to underline the meaning of innovation created on the basis of users' needs, we present two contrasting slides.

We remind that currently children treat the study as an adventure, and the experience makes them want to come back.

resonance

infant warmer ...

We discuss the second example, which is described in detail here <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-PyY94ssSww>.

Note for the trainer: if a longer workshop is held during the conference, we recommend developing this part by presenting the film to the participants. If the workshop lasts 4 hours, only an example based on the film should be discussed.

Slide 20: Infant warmer film to extend the workshop <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-PyY94ssSww>

21

In 1980, Apple asked IDEO to develop a mouse for their radical new computer, the **Lisa**. Previous attempts at mouse design, by Douglas Englebart and Xerox PARC, yielded results that were too expensive and hard to make. The Apple mouse needed to be more reliable and cost 10 percent less than the earlier versions. To start, the design team created a cheaper, much-improved mechanism that would operate the mouse, and found that a complex, plastic "ribcage" would hold the pieces together. The team similarly tested and refined the mouse's other key components, from the audible and tactile click of the button to the rubberised coating on the ball. A record turntable spun for days, logging "mouse miles" to check the reliability of the electromechanical assembly.

The resulting mouse proved mechanically and economically sound and was changed only slightly when adapted for use with the first Macintosh computer. The basic mechanism design is used in virtually all mechanical mice produced to date.

Coffee break

we create solutions

2030

<https://upstarthr.com/2017/10/>

1. After the break, we ask the participants to stay in the same groups as during the Silly Cow exercise.
2. In a minute each group will be asked to design a new solution, which will be used in the near future, i.e. in 2030.

However, before we go on to this, we want to discuss the way we are going to work. We will use SCAMPER to this end.

SCAMPER

this method is usually used when we transform an already existing thing in search for innovation

- S – substituting something with something else
- C – combining
- A – adapting existing concepts to our idea
- M – modifying, e.g. the size
- P – putting to another use
- E – eliminating something
- R – reversing

We discuss: SCAMPER method is similar to brainstorm, but, as during brainstorm, just like in the Silly Cow, concepts are generated freely, it may fail to lead us to expected results. That is why we will use both methods for the purposes of today's task. You already know, more or less, what brainstorm is.

What is SCAMPER then?

The aim is to change, transform the existing idea, so that something new is developed out of it. We add something, remove something, we do not make up anything that has not existed before, we work on the

existing material. SCAMPER method consists of several steps; whose first letters form its name. Questions we should answer using this method are also assigned to these steps. The questions have been prepared for you in the form of a canvas, which will facilitate your work. Each of you will receive it in a minute. A table for the explanation and discussion will be used as a canvas for the work. Discuss the example of a blog.

An example of a blog, support during the discussion

S – we replace texts with videos or infographics

C – we can combine standard entries with podcasts (there will be a podcast link next to the text)

A – we analyse paper press and, for example, update the blog with a single, long text published once a month

M – e.g.: size and we publish single-sentence entries once a day

P – e.g. find another target group and, for example, make it available in hard copy for elderly people

E – eliminate, for example, writing, if you don't like it

R – reverse, for example, the manner of work – write in the morning rather than in the evening, reverse the party who decides about the topic – readers instead of the author etc.

SCAMPER CANVA

the right column contains
questions that will help us
generate new solutions

COMPONENT/EXPLANATION	QUESTIONS ASKED DURING THE BRAINSTORM
S (SUBSTITUTE) We try to replace a fragment of an idea with another one. That is why we should know what elements are included in our idea and what can be replaced.	Which fragment can be replaced? What can it be replaced with? How can we do it? Does the idea have any substitutes?
C (COMBINE) We combine the idea we are working on with another one. We have to realize what has to remain unchanged.	What ideas can we combine? What can we combine them with? Is it possible to cooperate with other people? What will be the result of the combination?
A (ADAPT) We think whether any solutions that will help us solve the problem are available and apply them to our idea?	Has anyone else worked on a similar idea? Is there a solution that we can copy and adjust to our idea? Is there a person who we can follow and who we want to equal?
M (MAGNIFY) We change the colour, appearance, increase the size, shape.	Is there anything that can be increased? Which fragment should be properly underlined? What can be changed? Is there anything that can change the shape, size?
P (PUT TO ANOTHER USE) – use for a different purpose We change the target group, application, possibilities.	How the idea can be used? How a given item can be used? To which other target group could it be useful? How will it be used by a particular target group?
E (ELIMINATE) If it's clear if all fragments are necessary, which of them can be eliminated.	How can the idea be simplified? Which fragments can be eliminated? Which elements are in abundance? What would happen if we eliminated any of the fragments?
R (REVERSE) We try to reverse everything completely, turn it upside down, change everything we can.	How would a different order work? Can it be changed? What would happen if we used mirroring?

25

Distribute the canvas.

- ON THE LEFT side of the canvas, you will find a short explanation of every SCAMPER rule.
- ON THE RIGHT, there are more detailed questions. They will help you work on the development of an improved solution.

We select any example to explain the participants how they should work with questions, e.g. a tooth brush. We ask the participants to read the explanation to REPLACE principle aloud. Then we start a short conversation.

- Which fragment of a tooth brush can be replaced? (the head).
- What can it be replaced with? (a dental floss, a pipe for pressurised air).
- How can we do it? (with another head).
- Does the idea have any substitutes (yes, a dental floss, Waterpik).

Having discussed examples, you should ask the group whether they understand how to use the set of questions. When the group understands what kind of tool SCAMPER is, we can discuss brainstorm principles as presented on the next slide.

brainstorm – principles

moderator	we don't judge
quantity	we don't discuss whether it is possible or not
splurge, every idea	one idea, one post-it
to the point	we write clearly with a marker

We read aloud and discuss every principle shortly, providing a short comment.

moderator – It is a person who takes care about the the group's comfort of work. It is her/him who initiates the agreement on the rules of work, that is, who reads questions from the canvas. Who writes them down (everyone writes down their ideas or one person notes down)? The moderator controls the time.

Quantity: our aim is to generate as many ideas as possible

- **splurge, every idea:** We provide every idea that comes to our mind, it can inspire other group members. We also talk about ideas that can seem absurd.
- **to the point:** all ideas are acceptable provided that they are related to the subject of brainstorm
- **we don't judge:** we try to avoid judging statements, both positive ones, like “great idea”, and negative ones, like “it's not gonna work”.

one idea, one post-it + we write clearly: these are principles that enable easier classification of ideas after the end of work

mobile phone 2030

debit card 2030

the moderator controls the time: 21 min

we work more than 3 minutes on every component

we write down our ideas on a post-it

after 3 minutes the moderator asks the participants to go on to the next component

<https://upstarthr.com/2017/10/>

27

1. The trainer asks the group to select one solution they will work on.

2. Then we provide instructions to the task:
 - for the next 21 minutes, we will work according to brainstorm principles
 - That is why we ask the groups to select their moderators now. Once moderators have been selected, we continue the instruction
 - We explain that we will work on the improvement of the existing solution for 21 minutes altogether
 - There will be 7 rounds within the time limit of 21 minutes
 - Each round will be related to a different SCAMPER component and will last 3 minutes
 - During one round, we ask questions following the pattern provided in a given Scamper component
 - We write down the ideas on a post-it
 - We go on to the next component only after 3 minutes.
 - The work will be summed up at an adequate moment, once it has been finished.

Note: we recommend that the trainer announces the beginning of the work of all teams simultaneously and announces the beginning of a new round every three minutes. Although it's moderators who should take care of it, such support will ensure better dynamics of the work and greater transparency.

once the work has been
finished, we select the best
solution(s)

5 min

Once the work has been finished, we ask the teams to review their ideas and select ones that have the greatest potential in their opinion. It will be presented as a single, consistent whole in front of the group.

speed dating simulation

team

imagine you take part in the speed dating event

team has 45 seconds to present the idea to the partner

audience

everyone can spend 1 000 euro

we do not invest in our own team

two investment rounds

it will be the first capital entry

The trainer assumes the role of a speed dating partner and simulates space. He/she can ask the participants to measure the time or do it himself/herself. After 45 seconds trainer ends the presentation and invite next team/participant for the speed date.

Slide shown during speed dating. Once the conversations (all the speed dating) have been finished, write down how much individual teams earned. We can invite participants to come up to flipcharts and enter amounts that they decided to invest themselves. Looking at the numbers, we can reconstruct the discussion

- What was the main reason why you decided to invest in team X?
- Why didn't you invest in team Y?
- What would convince you to invest in team Y?

Trainer introduces to the workshop element of competition. It always stimulates all participants and increase engagement.

Anna Karenina vs. presentations, say what?

“all good presentations are the same, and every bad one is bad in its own way”

At this point we are opening a discussion on which of the elements must appear in every presentation.

“All good presentations are the same and each bad one is bad in its own way” is a paraphrase of the first sentence opening *Anna Karenina* novel by Leo Tolstoy: “All happy families are similar; every unhappy family is unhappy in its own way”. This sentence inspired a scientifically proven rule, the so-called Anna Karenina principle. The rule describes a situation in which the lack of one of required conditions leads to the inability to achieve the result. As a consequence, only a competitor who did not encounter any significant obstacles or the one who did not forget about any factor required to gain victory. Similar concept is expressed in Liebig's law of the minimum. Trainer may use the image of a barrel — often called "Liebig's barrel" — to explain Liebig's law. Just as the capacity of a barrel with staves of unequal length is limited by the shortest stave, so a plant's growth is limited by the nutrient in shortest supply. We use "One sentence Pitch" as a model. We show next slide when discussion with participant is over.

how to talk about an idea

customer, target group

problem

solution/gain

know how / secret sauce

money ?

My company is called Aeroo and we are working on a social platform to help frequent fliers book appropriate places by means of a single click on Facebook

We know basic elements that we cannot forget about in our presentation. They comprise the so-called one sentence pitch structure eg. Aeroo.

one sentence pitch

MY COMPANY ----- (company name)-----
WORKS ON ----- (solution type)-----
TO HELP ----- (determine the target group)-----
 ----- (describe the problem) -----
BY----- (uniqueness of the activities)-----

Coffee break

Slide 35:

Micoryza video film to extend the workshop <https://player.vimeo.com/video/62804907>

Since we know what elements should be included in a good presentation, let us look at a very good presentation.

DISCUSSING THE FILM

I'm Cindy and at Micoryza we've created a Kickstarter for Research. Cindy does not waste time to introduce herself with her full name and surname, she does not try to gain artificial recognition by saying that she is a CEO and does not torture us with a lame introduction like: I would like to tell you about an app. She immediately starts with a so-called high concept pitch and says that they have created a Kick-starter for Research. Thus she refers to a commonly known mechanism and a commonly known (successful) design. After this single sentence, it is already clear what they have created. A crowdfunding platform financing research and development. Easy! In theory. Try to sum up your company or your design with a single sentence, which could be placed on the reverse side of a business card.

Yesterday we've discovered that we were the top story on Reddit. The internet wants what we're building.

Then Cindy uses a social proof and the fact that they were a top story at Reddit to show... traction. The Internet wants the things we create. One can obviously argue and have doubts as to whether it is the best proof that someone needs this project, but the use of Reddit in the USA is a good idea. The users are really critical and astute observers, so one point goes to Cindy. Investors are interested in traction, that is, that people liked the product, it was accepted or there are premises that it will be accepted. And they really do not care about your estimates or intuition. They need proofs. In the form of a social proof, numbers, rather than faith or digressions.

Today research funding is broken. Funders are so conservative that they only fund the most obvious ideas.

We, we fund the long tail ideas. Another step and other simple (it's important) tasks. Cindy changes her tone a bit to present the problem. The research financing system sucks, and investors are so conservative that they finance only obvious projects. Cindy says that THEY want to finance research based on long tail ideas. If you have ever been interested in on-line business, you know this principle. I guess investors listening to Cindy also knew it. Long Tail is a concept formulated by Chris Anderson in October 2004 in an article for *Wired* magazine. It says that having an extensive product range can generate higher total sales on single, rarely searched for items than on the most popular goods sold in bulk. That's it. A metaphor of a long tail is PERFECT for this design.

We know that individuals want to give directly to science because our users are paying us. Over the past weeks we've doubled the transactions and research and users.

Traction again. It simply works. Cindy explains in simple terms that they have verified their hypothesis and that individual users want academic research to be financed. She does not talk rubbish about shared economy, does not show complicated business models, but simply provides the facts. Facts supporting design objectives.

Researchers from Stanford and Harvard and Yale and 25 other top universities are using Microryza instead of applying for grants.

This time several names that ruin the system are listed. There is nothing better than Stanford, Harvard and Yale. After all, who can be impressed by the clients of these centres that choose Cindy's design instead of applying for grants.

Then Cindy says how the design came into existence. She presents her personal story based on storytelling.

She begins strongly. ***I dropped out of grad school so that I could build Microryza.*** that is, I left the safe land of the university to support the creation of a promise land for researchers. However, everything that happens in the subsequent minutes fits the structure of Cambell's myth. One can laugh, but it works. Then Cindy goes further and shows three other stories. Stories that would come to a bad end if it wasn't for Microryza. These stories are dramatic and are built on the same pattern: a strong problem, strong areas and a happy end thanks to Microryza. and, finally... the icing on the cake. There is also a quotation of Bill Gates and a great conclusion: ***We're Microryza and we're democratising the research.*** We democratise research. That's great.

In a 3-minute pitch there was no request to sign an NDA (yes, I have once witnessed such a situation), there was no business plan, no marketing and talking rubbish about broadly defined promotion in social media. There was a simple concept, very simple sentences, traction shown twice and 3 stories, which would really come to a bad end if it wasn't for Microryza (currently known as Experiment). And there was Cindy, who presented it properly and calmly. And that's it. As much as that.

To conclude:

- The participants prepared short presentations
- We have seen how we should not present
- We spoke about model presentation

It is time to draw conclusions and prepare presentations once again, taking into account the discussed elements. The trainer adds a short comment to each element.

One liner – it can be, for example, one sentence pitch

problem – determining issues that are the most challenging for the customer, we try to be convincing, so that the problem is understood by all members of the audience, even those who are not involved in it. We can use storytelling here. Referring to a real or a fictitious situation, which will help understand the challenge the customer is facing

Solution – we clearly inform how we are going to solve the above-mentioned problem

Value proposition – what the customer will be willing to pay for? We specify the value that we offer, e.g. a set of services, safety, etc.

Competition – we do not forget to mention what the current market looks like

business model / traction – what we will earn on, which phase of works we are in, what we have managed to achieve. As the projects have just come into existence, the teams do not have to be focused on traction.

Team – investors focus both on the idea and the team that develops it. That is why you have to persuade them that your team is able to implement the undertaking that it has started.

During your work, you can also remember about elements such as:

- **strong visual communication**, e.g. underlining the value, numbers, graphs, presenting the situation before and after the application of the solution.
- **Social proof**.

preparation for the second investment round

the presentation is 5 minutes long
this time we are convincing a group
of investors

We give each team 15 minutes for the preparation of the second presentation. Each team will have 5 minutes to present: they can use post-its, flipcharts and other gadgets that can be useful during the presentation

Presentations...

Once we have finished the presentation, we ask the participants once again to invest in the solution that they find the most interesting. We remind that this time they have to spend the entire pool that is left from EUR 1000. We conclude by deciding which of the teams was the most convincing.

AND THE WINNER IS ...

We announce the winner and give the team a prize that we have prepared earlier: sweets, etc.

WHAT HAVE YOU
LEARNED?

The trainer initiates a discussion on the workshop, asking the participants e.g.:

What was the most difficult moment of the workshop in their opinion?

What was the most pleasant moment of the meeting?

What lesson have they learned?

Conclusion

The trainer mentions the elements of the workshop that will be elaborated on during the following meetings:

- A component concerning the user's needs illustrated on examples: infant warmer or MRI – Customers Development, Customer Discovery classes;
- Value proposition, that is, identifying elements that the customer is willing to pay for – Business Model Canvas.
- Design, iterative, lean thinking - Entrepreneurial Mind-set classes. What does it make an entrepreneur? etc.

4. Conclusions

The workshop "User Experience" aims to equip researchers with skills and tools that help them successfully understand the importance of *User Experience* in the design of a product or process, identify indicators of success, plot the customer journey using the '*talking out loud*' method, and identify, classify and prioritise changes to be made. The workshop "International Conference" is an opportunity to offer the researches a summarized perspective of the skills and tools needed to put their results in the market. Once the participants fully understand the opportunities these tools provide, they will be able to successfully commercialize their research findings.